

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

First Cycle Recommendations

WP7_D7.5

Version 1.1

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Advisory Board meeting 2
WP10_D10.3

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1. Introduction

The WYRED project (netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society) (García-Peñalvo, 2016b, 2017; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016) aims to provide a framework for research in which children and young people can express and explore their perspectives and interests in relation to digital society, but also a platform (Durán-Escudero, García-Peñalvo, & Therón-Sánchez, 2017; García-Peñalvo, 2016a; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017; García-Peñalvo, García-Holgado, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & Seoane-Pardo, 2018) from which they can communicate their perspectives to other stakeholders effectively through innovative engagement processes.

The object of the present report is to show the first recommendations from children and YP that participated at WYRED project during the 1st Cycle of the programme.

We need to state here and already mentioned in previous reports, that partners found some difficulties in terms of young participants engagement in the activities and that is the reason why all different groups and participants have achieved different levels of accomplishment with their research activities.

After the Social Dialogues sessions carried out by each partner in their respective countries, different groups of children and young people identified several topics and areas of discussion to start with their research activities.

The Dialogues engendered lively and energetic debate among young people – the themes presented by the facilitators were based on the Delphi questionnaire topics mainly – however other areas of interest outside the digital society were also discussed and raised as issues of priority. Some partners identified possible research questions/areas of foci under the prioritized themes.¹

Here, we aim to show the first topics of researches and conclusions or thoughts from the young participants around the themes they have been exploring and learning about. independently of the status of their research process, whether they came out with a specific artefact or idea, the intention is to list all topics and the artefacts some of them have created.

Below, all projects are listed with their remarks.

¹ WP5_D5.2, Key Research Questions; Early Years, 2017

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Few numbers of this 1st Cycle:

- **280 participants**
- **92 projects**
- **young participants from 8 to 10 and 13 to 23 years old**

2. Background - Previous topics identified by participants

Before presenting the actual projects and recommendations from the 1st Cycle of Research Activities, it is interesting to see whether the topics of discussion from the previous Social Dialogues sessions and the actual topics or themes chosen by participants correspond, have changed and how they have evolved into their actual research processes.

Prioritized Topics during Social Dialogues sessions	Topics/Research questions 1st Cycle
<p>Boundaries - UK</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Discipline and rules in education ● Self-Image and self confidence ● Tolerance to different cultures/opinions ● Jobs that are available for under 18's ● Internet safety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Education ● Healthcare
<p>PYE - UK</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Populist politics ● Money and happiness ● Travelling ● Living a full and varied life ● Food – food miles, cooking and eating together ● Lowering legal age to vote ● Brexit impact ● General election ● Authentic feminism ● Refugee situation in UK ● Empathy through communication and understanding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Housing in Brighton ● Manual Labourers ● Gambling ● Video Violence ● Music ● Genre Stereotypes ● Streetwear from Sweatshops ● Faces of Brighton - How multicultural is your community? ● 4am in Brighton ● Young Smokers ● How does technology affect children?

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LGBT rights, same sex marriage • Cannabis – positive and negative effects • Making bad choices • Role of parents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loneliness • Phishing online • Cost of Living • Homelessness
<p>USAL - Spain</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender stereotypes and discrimination • Tolerance to different cultures/opinions • Necessary changes in education • Cyber bullying and shaming • Internet safety and privacy • Emotional education and internet • Causes of stress among young people • Self-image and self confidence • Internet and social media risks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender stereotypes and discrimination • Feminism • Minorities • Globalisation • Politics • Environment • Religion • Social Media • Nationalism • Identity
<p>EARLY YEARS - Northern Ireland</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-Image and self confidence • Cyber bullying and shaming • Internet safety and privacy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children behavior on internet
<p>MOVES - Austria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental problems • Future Technologies • Nuclear Power • Cyber-Bullying • Future Prospects • Waste of food • Media literacy • Maritime Pollution • Education • Tolerance for other countries • Live, like I want to live • Mobbing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pollution on the air or sea-level or pollution coming from cars • Education system in Austria • Modern Technologies - and their Effects on Tourism Industry • Effects of Industry 4.0 on Tourism Industry - Development from E-Tourism to M-Tourism • Employment and jobs for young people • Legal rights • Mobbing

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education • Stress: • Animal protection • Human trafficking • Reutilization of resources • Thoughts for life • What I love 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youtube and Gaming
<p>OXFAM - Italy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education • Tolerance to different cultures/opinions • Integration of migrants/refugees in schools and society • Internet safety and privacy • Gender stereotypes and discrimination • Self-image • Causes of stress for young people • Changes in education system • Cyberbullying • Role of families and friends • Sociability and social media • globalisation: photography denounce • how Italy is seen by other countries • youth relationship with labour market • youth and political participation • integration of young migrants in schools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youth, media and self-representation • Youth, labour market and political participation • globalisation and social inclusion
<p>YEU - Belgium</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Necessary changes in education • Tolerance • Employment • Integration • Role of parents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Causes of stress • Employment perspective • Necessary Changes in Education • Internet Safety and Privacy • Gender Stereotypes

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self -image • Gender Stereotypes • Internet Safety • Cyberbullying • Media Literacy • Causes of Stress • Adults' misunderstanding • Tolerance towards other Cultures/Opinions • Integration of migrants and Refugees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tolerance towards different Cultures/Opinions
<p>DOGA - Turkey</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity • City challenges: cosmopolitan city & air pollution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental issues (e.g. pollution, water consumption) • Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions • Employment prospects • Self-image and self-confidence aspects
<p>TAU - Israel</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes required in education • Self-image and self-confidence • Privacy and security on the Internet • Cyberbullying and shaming on the Internet • Tolerance to different opinions and cultures • Causes of distress among young people 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What's wrong with the education system and how it can be improved • TransMed group/community
<p>Prioritized Topics from Delphi Results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-image and self-confidence • Tolerance to different cultures/opinions • Necessary changes in education • Mental wellbeing • Media literacy, namely the reliability of information on the internet and in social media 	

3. Research topics & recommendations from the 1st Cycle

All partners have implemented different sessions and activities with the groups of children, YP and stakeholders to work on the research processes. Some groups have finalized with their research and can provide already some conclusions and/or artefacts and others are still in processes.

Here are listed all projects from the 1st Cycle, independently of their status of completion, together with comments and recommendations from participants when a available.

Supporting materials such as pictures and videos and the actual artefacts uploaded to the WYRED Platform are listed on the Annexes.

	Country	Topic / Name of the project	Status	Comments/Conclusions
1	UK	Cost of living & housing in Brighton, UK	Finished	<p>Very valuable to learn about the real costs of living, in terms of renting and utility bills, and that such practical information would be helpful for other teens as part of their education</p> <p>Raise of homelessness and how Brighton seemed to have noticeably more people living rough on the streets. Homelessness had doubled in the last year and was second in the country only to London</p> <p>Empathy for those he saw on the streets who couldn't find affordable housing or were dealing with other issues</p>
2	UK	Gambling	Ongoing: photo essays complete	<p>Still in the research phase but have made some discoveries about the nature of online gambling. The services offered by the online gambling vendors serve to perpetuate gambling addiction. One young man commented there</p>

			Docs in progress. They are looking to upload their projects and generate discussion around the topics	should be more services available to help people who are addicted to gambling and accruing more debts than they can afford and education for young people about the services available to help young people be aware of the dangers and the importance of asking for help and support.
3	UK	Manual Labourers Video Violence Music Genre Stereotypes Streetwear from Sweatshops Faces of Brighton - How multicultural is your community? 4am in Brighton Young Smokers How does technology affect children?	Ongoing: photo essays complete, Docs in progress. They are looking to upload their projects and generate discussion around the topics	Discussion on how to frame questions as research projects. Different methods of research available. What would you ask other YP in Europe to respond to your project
4	UK	How can yoga help young people in the digital age?	Starting, ongoing and finished	<p>Reflexion and research process on how yoga helps YP. They carried out a survey of attitudes to yoga in one of the participants schools. They created a blueprint for yoga in education which they presented to 110 people at a yoga and education conference in London, a shared vision of what how yoga could be incorporated into the curriculum.</p> <p>As a result of this, the coordinator of team was invited to participate in the UK All Party Parliamentary Group on Yoga in education, healthcare, the workplace and prisons, which is working on how to incorporate yoga into policy in these areas. It is important that the voice of the young is being heard at these levels of policy and that they are part of the conversation.</p> <p>The notion of the digital society was very much in the background. When asked they recognized the influence of</p>

				social media, for example, on their lives and stress levels, but saw it as simply part of the context, as opposed to an issue in itself.
5	Northern Ireland	Why do children tell lies on the internet?	Finished	<p>The research produced a range of theories around this. 79% of the respondents if they told lies did so told because they felt left out by their friends. 67% if they told lies did so because they did things online that they didn't want their parents to know about. Despite this however 73% of respondents declared they were actually honest online. Overall 80% of respondents did not think it was ok to tell lies on the internet. Well done Cycle 1 participants for researching telling lies online and providing evidence that being a good digital citizen is alive in NI from our group of respondents.</p> <p>Main conclusion children arrived to is that internet is made to be more transparent in revealing people's true identities</p>
6	Austria	Appeal to the European Parliament on renewable enrgies	Finished	<p>Importance of renewable energies for the future world. Specifically they talk about hydropower and solar-energy. They provide Chinese examples ("Donghai Bridge Wind Farm" or "Panda Power Plant") for combating climate change and invite the European Union to see the perspective of enhancing environmentally sustainable energy resources. They provide a suggestion how to make agricultural areas available for wind turbines, high altitude wind power and solar power by assuring with a legal act, that every member state will provide a certain percentage of the agricultural area in order to generate green power.</p>
7	Austria	Prison School - "Gefängnis Schule"	Finished	<p>There are already several dynamic teachers being innovative in didactics and methodology. However, this is just one side of the medal respectively one step. The other side is the system itself which in the way described above involves parents, teachers and young people. As a further important step it is described democratic, alternative school forms like for example "Kapriole in Freiburg", "The free school in Leipzig" which focus on children's and young people's´ individual resources with teachers being empowering "Learning-Coaches", also focusing on peer-learning and and bringing back curiosity to the learners.</p> <p>Maybe this is not the ultimate solution for our old-crusted system, but it takes the right direction. We need to start learning, understanding, exploring and researching again.</p>

				The people of tomorrow need a school of tomorrow.
8	Austria	Modern Technologies - and their Effects on Tourism Industry	Finished	Analysis of the new technologies (list), which are relevant for the tourism industry. The research identifies three forms of modern technology impacting the tourism industry: Virtual Reality, Algorithms, and Robotics and briefly explain their effects.
9	Austria	Effects of Industry 4.0 on Tourism Industry - Development from E-Tourism to M-Tourism	Finished	Research based on the idea from E-Tourism to M-Tourism. Based on recent tendencies, online travel agencies will be more likely to be used instead of travel agencies. Which does not necessarily mean that travel agencies will completely fade from the market.
10	Austria	Modern Slavery	Finished	Illustration of the disastrous working-conditions of foreign-workers in Dubai, being one of the column for the enormous per capita income of the inhabitants.
11	Austria	Trade agreements within the European Union	Finished	The research shows the impacts of the CETA agreement between the EU and Canada on different levels and understand by this why these agreements are of high importance to the future economy, which means to YP. The authors invite to discuss about the topic..
12	Austria	Gaming	Finished	Fascination on gaming has for them in presenting the voices of rappers. It turns out that this has a lot to do with being a valuable part of a community. A member of a community who is appreciated and who's contribution to the game is regarded as a being welcomed and wanted
13	Austria	Sedetka- this is my life	Finished	Reflections on life from a teenager (texts, reflections, statements)
14	Austria	Environmental Pollution	Finished	Reminder and showing the dangers of nuclear power plants
15	Austria	Future Professions	Finished	Young teenagers express their feeling about their future employments
16	Austria	Mobbing	Finished	Thoughts and a call from young people regarding mobbing in their environments
17	Austria	Don't give up	Finished	Considerations and thoughts from a teenager about following its aims and dreams and encourage other to follow their dreams and try to achieve them
18	Italy	What's originate	Ongoing	Usually we think about young people as the happiest and

		stress in young people?		<p>free generation of earth: they don't have particular commitments apart from studying. But, often after school they have sport, extra-curricular activities and for some people even a job.</p> <p>Young people today are pushed to develop more and more competences in order to compete in society with other young people.</p> <p>If we add also the component related to their social condition their lives are even more complicated.</p> <p>For this reason most of young people admit to be stressed, how do they cope with it?</p>
19	Italy	How do institutions support schools against cyber bullying?	Finished	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bullying today takes place mainly on social media but the effects are visible in real life. Students have identified a bullied person as someone who introverted, isolated and weak. • At national level schools are creating partnerships with the police to train young people about the use of internet and its laws, but young people affirm that schools should have a more direct role in terms of inclusion, support and direct confrontation. • Teachers, instead affirm that for them is quite difficult to detect the phenomenon in class.
20	Italy	How have the digital era and the economic crisis revolutionised the relationship between youth and labour market?	Finished	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tendency of individualism among young people. They consider their own working condition as personal and specific. This allow a naïve positivity that can be a stimulus, but it doesn't allow young people to feel part of a common category. • Following this attitude, the survey shows that they are not aware of youth unemployment issue, its dimensions and implications at sociological and political level.
21	Italy	Citizens' social and electoral participation	Finished	<p>Mathematical analysis of social participation and vote based on a questionnaire. It wanted to show how we vote, the thought of people about old generations, the relationship between social participation and vote, the perception of social involvement and how we can improve it.</p> <p>Findings: the more people perceive as important</p>

				participating in society, the more they get engaged. It is interesting that among the interviewed, the most engaged in society didn't vote for the Italian national elections.
22	Italy	How does fear for the employment future influences our present reality?	Finished	<p>The research focuses on young people's perception of future in relation to employment uncertainty. The results of the survey administered to young people from high schools to young workers have raised several reflections:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The high unemployment standards scared Italian youth population and with regret everyone dreams to move abroad as soon as possible. • Few people know about the meaning of NEET, this means that they are not aware of their condition, therefore they don't advocate for policy change. <p>The interviewed propose to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • stimulate hiring, reform third sector, create new didactic programmes with synergies with external world, working experiences controlled by the State, fight against illegal work, reconsider contracts and create programmes to support job research.
23	Italy	Youth and political participation	Finished	<p>Following a desk research and the administration of a survey among young people, the final reflections are the following:</p> <p>On a side there is a crisis of participation and care of institution towards young people's needs and ambitions that needs to be analysed through its social and economic aspects. On the other side there is a crisis of young people's concept of identity and belonging to a generational group, which finds expression through fine art and other types of participation.</p>
24	Italy	What does democracy mean?	Ongoing	<p>Among the evidences of the survey:</p> <p>Today's individualism at any cost leads directly or indirectly to political apathy in building our own identities and striving for individual success.</p> <p>Dominant ideology is trying to destroy any precedent collective obligation, starting from sub-cultures through fashion standardisation to the Fordist employment model in decline due to the tertiary model of European economies (but a country cannot live of ICT and tourism).</p>

25	Italy	Globalisation. ONG's denounce and photographic evidence	Finished	Photographic denounce is a research framed into the macro issues of globalisation and social inequalities. Photography is a tool used by many NGOs to denounce such inequalities. The research aims to find out the level of concern of young people and adults towards this issue with a specific focus on the emotive sphere. The results show that despite the fact young people see a lot of images with detailed attention, they tend not to get very emotional about what they see as they receive too many inputs on a daily basis.
26	Italy	Integration of young migrants in school	Ongoing	The research aims to investigate among schoolmates with migrant background their role as intercultural mediators between the family and the outer society through workshops and theatre.
27	Italy	How is Italy seen by other countries?	Finished	The aim of this research is to understand how Italy and Italians are seen by other Countries; if usual stereotypes - regarding what people throughout the world think about Italian culture - are reliable or not, and what first comes to foreigners' mind when they think about Italy. It seems that Italians are seen always happy and having a good quality of life, but when tourists come to Italy often change their ideas due to all the things that don't work properly.
28	Italy	What has changed over the last 10 years, if it has changed, in the perception of people of different cultures?	Ongoing	Due to the wave of racism and stereotypes of the political discourse that affected public opinion perception of people with migratory background, this research investigates inside the family and among friends if and how the perception of immigrants has changed over the last 10 years.
29	Israel	What's wrong with the education system and how it can be improved.	Finished Artefact planned and conceptualise, to be realized in May 2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Listening to young persons and understand them in order to alleviate the burden that students experience. They should come not just to hear us but also to really listen. • Changing the education approach and the curriculum. Reducing the workload and more consideration of students' private lives. • To open the possibility for students to choose the topics

				<p>of learning, namely allowing them to choose the subjects of study in a broader manner.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce the number of compulsory subjects. • Changing the reform done in the high school curriculum, returning the start of matriculation exams to 10-th grade, and distributing the exams over the three years in high school. • The implementation of so-called “meaningful learning” in a clearer and broader sense. • To stop causing the students to just “throw up” the learned material, with an emphasis on changing the teacher-student relationship. • Especially to emphasize the significant reduction of pressure on high school students and the expansion of their activity possibilities after the school hours.
30	Israel	Transformative Media in Israel	Starting, activity on the platform	No comments available yet
31	Italy/ Belgium	The relationship between digital identity and stress in young people - Does Digital Identity (life in SM) lead to stressful behaviour in real life?	Ongoing	No comments available yet
32	Italy/ Belgium	Which level is better to cover employment prospects	Finished	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • comparing local to international level on the topic of employment prospects, participants believe that the link between local and international is the solution; • There is a huge necessity to change education systems, however the issue of linkage to technology gathers the least “support”; • Majority of young people who took part, see themselves migrating for working purposes.

33	Italy/ Belgium	The use of Digital as content in Education	Finished	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote and raise awareness within stakeholders on the fact that education cannot be separated from technology, as it plays an increasingly preponderant role in today's reality; • Promote the introduction of digital tools into education, as it can optimize learning time, provide greater teaching support and improve quality; • Need to link education to technological innovations. Doing so and granting access to these technologies can shape new habits and new types of learning; • Also, linking education to the digital innovations can lead to the development of different approaches locally and globally.
34	Italy/ Belgium	Are young people aware of privacy and safety aspect when being online?	Finished	<p>The majority of young people think that internet, today, is very useful because makes easy our modern lifestyle. They think also that all types of excess can be a danger so excessive use of internet could be dangerous and it can make you a "social addicted". If internet is used in the right way it could bring only advantages. For sure internet has an impact on our behavior and social interactions</p>
35	Belgium	What is the impact of Social Media on building awareness and understanding around gender and gender identities?	Ongoing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To a small extend there are some sources that do promote understanding and awareness; • There are a lot of aggressive and "hate" related messages online; • There is the need to promote a gender sensitive educational approach online and offline from early years; • Link Formal Education and Non-Formal Education to promote online sources on education, support and awareness on the matter of gender and gender identities.
36	Italy/ Belgium	Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions through the eyes of children: how are differences perceived?"	Ongoing	No conclusions yet

37	Italy/ Belgium	Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions: cultural development - can the virtual/digital tools help? how?	Finished	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on multilingual approaches and learning; • Promote the value of diversity, understood as cultural and human enrichment, that can lead to the concept of integration; • Foster initiatives and commit to the promotion of inclusive ecosystems in education and venues (e.g. Libraries), while offering a dialogue with local administrations; • Promote the use of virtual spaces and digital tools as they indeed help (digital books, online courses, technological tools in education etc).
38	Italy/ Belgium	Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions from an intergenerational perspective: online generation vs. offline generation	Ongoing	No recommendations yet
39	Italy/ Belgium	Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions at school - what's the perception of migrant students and how does the virtual world affect reality on this topic?	Ongoing	<p>The research tackles the perception of young Italian and foreign students on the subject of tolerance towards opinions and cultures which are "different from theirs." How is diversity in the classroom and in the non-school environment? How is the theme dealt within the family? What do they learn from the media?</p> <p>Objective: To investigate the perception and opinion of middle school children about the issues of tolerance and discrimination by referring to their personal experience</p>
40	Spain	La lucha de la existencia	Finished	YP need to find their own identity and build their own values. They refuse to be tagged as selfish, materialistic, by adults who probably do practice these attitudes.

				YP do not resign themselves to adopting a conformist attitude and struggle to change the world in which they live
41	Spain	El efecto de la globalización en la educación	Finished	Even in a global world, education is still under control of governments, which in many cases deliberately manipulate people through education. It is crucial to develop open, free and critical educational systems to avoid manipulation
42	Spain	Starbucks Rwanda Rift Valley	Finished	Globalization and media (specially smartphones) are changing our world in such a way as to compete with primary instances of socialization (family, school) and so having increasing importance
43	Spain	Feminismo, inmigración ilegal, Sociedad y tradición	Finished	Feminism is a necessary and global movement in our time
44	Spain	Ni una menos	Finished	Feminism is about past and present, but is above all future
45	Spain	Una nueva Europa	Finished	Education, initiative and exchange between nations are the principles that should guide the youth in building a new Europe.
46	Spain	The face of society	Finished	In a globalized society, consumerist and permanently attached to technology and mobile phones, young people have to find their place in the world, their own identity, unique and non-transferable, individual and intimate.
47	Spain	El impacto de la globalización	Finished	Faced with the phenomenon of influencers and the use of social networks, especially in the construction of the individual identity of adolescents, the influence of the family context on the construction of the vocation and personal identity is valued.
48	Spain	Homofobia	Finished	Through a history of homophobia, a reflection on the reasons why it continues to exist in our days is proposed, while pointing out the need to move towards the acceptance of sexual diversity.
49	Spain	Feminismo. ¿Cuánto sabe la gente?	Finished	How much do people know about feminism? It is a question for society in general, which young people have used to interview people of different ages on the street on issues related to feminism.
50	Spain	La realidad de nuestra naturaleza	Finished	We must be aware of the main environmental problems that affect our world, and that have affected us throughout history.

51	Spain	La desigualdad en sus distintos aspectos desde una visión global	Finished	Discrimination against women, racism and classism are the subject of research for young people who want to draw society's attention to three fundamental forms of inequality among human beings.
52	Spain	La sociedad	Finished	The evolution of the concept of society, the construction of identity and nationality, as well as the phenomenon of globalization are topics for discussion that young people want to share with policy makers in this project.
53	Spain	Globalización, nación e identidad en el mundo actual	Finished	Globalization confronts us with positive and negative elements in the construction of the concept of identity and nation.
54	Spain	Alumnas inspiradas	Finished	Write short stories can be a way of narrating one's vision of nation, personal identity and vision of a global world.
55	Spain	La redes sociales en un mundo globalizado	Finished	The forms of communication have evolved. What are the criticisms that society makes about novelties?
56	Spain	No nos olvidemos de la realidad	Finished	There are different perspectives in the analysis of the concepts of globalization, nation and identity, such as the philosophical, social and economic point of view.
57	Spain	El mundo actual	Finished	There is space for personal and groups' reflections in the analysis of the actual world
58	Spain	How to 3	Finished	Be aware of the difficulty of understanding the world around us.
59	Spain	Globalización desde nuestra ciudad	Finished	The effects of globalisation are around us, just look at your city.
60	Spain	Influencia de la educación en nuestra vida	Finished	It is important to know the evolution of education, to better understand our society.
61	Spain	Feminismo	Finished	It is necessary to reflect on feminism as an element of identity, as a national and global reality.
62	Spain	Un mar de plásticos	Finished	We have to take measures to save the environment.
63	Spain	Cuento	Finished	We can be separated by ideologies but united by feelings.
64	Spain	Radio Sol	Finished	The importance of social networks told in a podcast.

65	Spain	Paseo por la realidad	Finished	To know the phenomenon of nationalisms
66	Spain	La vida de Timmy	Finished	We must support young people in their struggle to identify their vocation and overcome the harassment of other colleagues.
67	Spain	La globalización en el mundo	Finished	There are “local” stereotypes on globalization to be analyzed in a more comprehensive way.
68	Spain	La globalización: origen y actualidad	Finished	Investigate the origins of globalization and its current importance to understand the current world.
69	Spain	Yihadismo	Finished	Investigate religious fanaticism to understand the origin of recent violent acts.
70	Spain	Cartas para no ser leídas	Finished	In a dystopian world, reflect on communication in a world in which the digital society has disappeared.
71	Spain	Un solo planeta	Finished	Reflect on the fundamental problems that affect our planet.
72	Spain	La Declaración unilateral de independencia de Cataluña. Historia de un nacionalismo	Finished	Reflect on the causes of the unilateral declaration of independence of Catalonia.
73	Spain	El terrorismo de ETA	Finished	Reflect on the meaning of the terrorist group ETA in the construction of Basque identity and nationalist conflicts in Spain.
74	Spain	Problemas de identidad personal	Finished	Reflect on the difficulties of inclusion of ethnic or religious minorities in our societies.
75	Spain	Guerra y evolución	Finished	Investigate the relations between three wars of the last 100 years, in order to establish relations between them.
76	Turkey	Not drawn a scale!	Finished	According to recent reports, about 1 billion people in the world lack access to clean drinking water and there are millions of people who suffer from water-related diseases annually. These figures make us think about that the hundreds of litres of water wasted each day. Innovative water saving product designs and prototypes might be useful in saving large quantities of drinking water from going to waste. All prototypes conceived to find an

				affordable solution to save water can help to preserve the environment. The idea behind all this is that if small changes are implemented by by many people, the overall impact can be huge.
77	Turkey	Filter machine	Finished	Prototype created
78	Turkey	Technological glove	Finished	Prototype created
79	Turkey	Smart filter	Finished	Prototype created
80	Turkey	Dentepate	Finished	This innovative system looked at the consumption of drinking water while brushing teeth. The solution is a device that optimises the amount of water used and, at the end of the mouth wash, separates waters from other waste products (e.g. toothpaste)
81	Turkey	Water cleaning device (WCD)	Finished	Prototype created
82	Turkey	Something cool	Finished	Prototype created
83	Turkey	Everything is better with air	Finished	Prototype created
84	Turkey	Rain arise	Finished	Recent researches show that households use over 400 litres of water every day of the week. Some innovative technologies can make a big dent in our water usage and our water bills. Smart homes give us insights that help us conserve energy, water, and resources. The idea is to design smart homes to reduce the burden on resources, by using them as efficiently as possible. Reservoirs and pipelines were rebuilt, and systems were designed to pump water to our homes.
85	Turkey	Master regülatör box	Finished	Prototype created
86	Turkey	Smart Water (SMWR)	Finished	Prototype created
87	Turkey	Miracle salt: the alternatives of new generation heat insulation with sodium sulfete	Finished	The results of an experiment conducted on a salt called sodium sulphate showed that it dissolves in water and that, when dissolved, it absorbs the heat from the environment and acts as an insulation. This leads to the idea of using sodium sulphate for the insulation of buildings. Globally, there is a great demand increase for energy, due to the

				<p>increase of the world's population. This need of energy is met from fossil fuel which, however, is already known to have harmful effects for humans and for the environment, not to mention its high cost. Therefore, the use of sodium sulphate to insulate houses can help reduce the need for energy. Since the salt will be produced locally in a sustainable production cycle, it will support the local economy to supply its own environmentally friendly products.</p>
88	Turkey	Don't be afraid know well!	Finished	<p>The results of the survey on the refugees in Turkey;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The increase in the refugee population causes feelings of insecurity among citizens. • The majority of Turkish citizens have prejudices and stereotypes about refugees. • The majority of people prefer to stay away from the refugees, and prefer not to use common areas. <p>As an outcome, it was stated that in order to overcome prejudices, citizens should be trained and well informed about the plight of refugees, so as to foster a peaceful co-living situation.</p>
89	Turkey	The population change, social and spatial effects after refugee migrations in the last ten years of istanbul	Finished	<p>This study looked at the problems connected to refugees and defectors . It is generally believed that they disturb the community structure in many aspects. At the end of the preliminary interview and workshops about 'minorities and respect of differences', it was shown that perception could be changed uniquely through education. It was determined that stereotypes were changed during the last interview at the end of workshops. The students who received the relevant training in the first focus group, showed off their sensitivity about this subject via posters, banners and leaflets they had prepared during the workshops.</p>
90	Turkey	The environmentally friendly roofs: to obtain energy from rain water on the roofs shaped in the form of m	Finished	<p>The use of renewable resources instead of fossil fuel has recently seen an upwards trend. The prototype created by the students aims to obtain energy from the water gathered on roofs, which are designed in the shape of an 'M' to collect as much rain as possible, to optimise hydroelectric resources. It was suggested that this energy resource should be disseminated in the regions with high levels of precipitation. Whilst this project can be obtained with an economical cost, regulating the speed of the water flowing from the roof is difficult. Overall, though, since the energy produced can be stored, the usages of this kind of roof should be increased and these stations should be</p>

				integrated with other renewable energies, such as wind, tidal waves, etc.
91	Turkey	Sex-oriented idioms from past to today	Finished	In the search conducted with the content analysis method, the detected 18 Turkish idioms contained negative comments about. It was seen that the status of women in society is perceived to be below men, from an intellectual and social aspect. The role of women in society is reduced to being a mother and a house keeper. The concept of equal rights could therefore not be appropriately developed, according to the examined idioms. Attempts should be made to decrease the frequency of occurrence of these fixed idioms that may or may not be used on purpose, but which surely are unhelpful to change society's point of view.
92	Turkey	Zero waste with <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Finished	The findings of the research show that of <i>chlorella vulgaris</i> can absorb carbon dioxide. In this project, <i>chlorella vulgaris</i> was used in factory chimneys to lower the water footprint, since it filters without leaving any biological waste. It also produces an alternative compost, which is completely environment friendly. The hope is to create a remedy against global warming.

4. Main topics of discussion and recommendations

Diversity of groups, ages, countries, cultures, methodologies etc, shows us a wide range of topics that children and young people have chosen in accordance to their values, interests and objectives.

This table summarises the main topics or areas of interest that young people have worked around on their researches in the 1st Cycle. The nature of the projects shows us the research exercises have brought the participants to a deep reflection on certain areas, not directly related to digital society at a first instance, but somehow connected.

Main topics:	Conclusions/Recommendations:
Internet & Security	Self-awareness by children and YP about internet and its relation with their self-image and relationship with parent sand adults YP need to face the challenge of being themselves in both real and digital world, and nobody is instructing them with regard to living in their digital environments The space/limits between online and offline world is not so clear; Not a lot of young people are aware of dangers and “rights” when it comes to the digital world
Internet & Social Media	Awareness about social media channels and how youth interact through these channels Dangers and social implication identified by young people and proposal of solutions for a healthy relationship with online life. Relevance on how YP express and communicate through these channels Youth need education or guidance on how to use and interpret

	images that constantly circulate and receive on social media
Digital society/world	<p>Young People tend to be ignored when creating policies and processes that have a direct impact on them (online or offline);</p> <p>There is lack of education and development of critical thinking in relevance to the digital world;</p> <p>The digital world might not be tangible but affects mindsets, culture and language;</p> <p>The online spaces seem to be more engaging rather offline/adult spaces;</p> <p>Not being heard by society leads to “speaking up” online and using that to share frustrations and connect to people</p>
Environment pollution	Awareness of world environmental issues and claim of International organisations action
Education	<p>Strong criticism around education system that generates strong frustration to students and demotivation regarding their aspirations and future</p> <p>Overload of school and after school duties. A change in School curricula is needed</p> <p>Education is about how to live, not about just information and contents (which can be easily founded on the internet). Emotional education is key to succeed in this (twofold) world</p> <p>Importance and need to incorporate more technology education in the curricula and access to technology</p>
Self-image	The individual is beyond the concepts of both Nation and Global. The self-image is challenging, but the other two concepts tend to be fuzzy
Wellbeing & Health	<p>Relevance of selfcare</p> <p>How yoga, education and society, and the different issues that young people are concerned about which include substance abuse, creativity, anger issues, media and others, but the most important shared concerns were the state of education, the state of the environment, and issues relating to mental health</p>

	Reasons of being stressed - pressure in nowadays societies and the role
Bullying	Schools should have a more direct role in terms of inclusion, support and direct confrontation Importance of the role of teachers as mentors and need of more training on this issue
Politics	Interest in the topic however the level of participation in elections is very low Need more active engagement from civil society in politics and on the other side, institutions need to focus more on youth needs & demands, as they don't feel represented by any group
Employment	Youth lack of interest and information about the actual labour situation and social and political consequences, however the high unemployment rates persist Youth ask for revisions and reform of hiring processes, training programs, revisions of labour laws and contracts to improve workers conditions
Culture and identity	Reflexion around culture and identity and the impact of stereotypes and prejudices on the mindset of young people Prevention programs are necessary to prevent problems around racism, discrimination and political troubles More initiatives/policies to promote an inclusive ecosystem (cultural, religion, sex orientation, languages, etc.)

5. The experience of the research process

One of the objectives of the WP7 is to know what young participants think about the project, their reflexions and feedback around the research process and activities.

After the research activity and process of the participants in this 1st Cycle, we can provide some feedback from children and young people that illustrates their satisfaction with the activity and they participation during the sessions held with facilitators.

The Evaluation Grids for participants created for this purpose where applied by few partners. Not all were able to use the template for each participant, however facilitators could observe the dynamics and participants attitudes during the sessions as exposed below.

UK: young participants from one area of the UK are very satisfied and committed to continuing the work, they are now coming into the platform to share a survey they have been working on for the next WYRED cycle. The core group was highly motivated though there were few participants that expressed interest but did not fully engage with the process, mainly for logistics.

The young people involved expressed high levels of satisfaction with the process and participation of the core group throughout was at a high level.

In some cases, the young people were enthusiastic, passionate and engaged throughout. They offered some sensitive reflections and had first hand experience to bear on the issues. There was trust, respect and humour throughout.

Northern Ireland: most of the children were very happy or feeling good about the activity. From facilitators perspective, children's participation was high.

Austria: most of the participants that filled in the evaluation grids rate their experience as good or very good, which their satisfaction regarding the activity very positive.

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Italy: informal feedback is very positive from all the participants thanks to the approach and the support given without interfering with their curiosity.

Belgium: participants were engaged and participated in all activities proposed. Although was a bit challenging by the fact of working with groups from different locations, the overall experience went well and young participants were happy with the project.

Spain: As a general consideration, level of participation and commitment of the young people has been high or very high. The students that took part in the making-of tell they have dedicated a significant number of hours to the development of the research, taking into account that they have had to use their spare-time (afternoons and weekends) from January to March 2018.

Also, the quality of the final products is generally good and, in some cases, excellent for content and creativity.

Israel: Overall the satisfaction of participants was high. The participants were very enthusiastic about the project. They met several times, prepared drafts, registered to the WYRED platform and are very interested to know what other groups in other countries are doing.

Turkey: The students' feedback was that they found the topics to be very interesting, and that they were eager to take further part in WYRED. At the beginning, some students had some difficulty in expressing their ideas, which may be due to a language barrier, as the session was delivered in English.

The workshop had been a big opportunity to observe different cultures and share opinions since, as it brought together students from 4 different countries. The students also experienced team work and practiced how to collaborate proficiently.

The participants think that they improved their creative confidence, they can express themselves in new ways, gained skills to boost creativity in their work and life, become inspired

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and gained the skills to inspire others. In summary, this two-day workshop enabled the students to think out-of-the-box and to develop skills which will be useful for business and life in general.

6. Conclusions

As conclusions of this 1st Cycle of Recommendations we list few aspects to highlight the research projects and the development of the project in the following cycle:

- Young people are engaged in all activities proposed and develop their own researches. Not always come with specific considerations or recommendations that can be transmitted to policy makers.
- Next steps after the researches projects are finished and artefacts created are to share their findings and recommendations and orient them where they can share and communicate what they have to say through different channels
- Different methodologies used during the research activities illustrated the diversity of each partner and countries and different way of working with youth
- Timing on carrying out the activities with young participants has been a big challenge for all partners. That's the reason why not all projects are on the same stage of completion and number of projects are very different
- The variety of topics and research questions show the inclusiveness of the project and it is a clear example of youth vision on different topics and areas of their interest

7. Annexes

7.1 List of finished projects

Compilations of some artefacts and illustration of the different research processes.

Project title: Cost of living & housing in Brighton, UK

Country: UK

Artefacts created: [https://en.wyredproject.eu/2018/02/19/brighton-housing-dialogue-expands-](https://en.wyredproject.eu/2018/02/19/brighton-housing-dialogue-expands-students-minds/)

[students-minds/](https://en.wyredproject.eu/2018/02/19/brighton-housing-dialogue-expands-students-minds/)

Project title: Why do children tell lies on the internet?

Country: Northern Ireland

Artefacts created:

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early years
netWorked Youth Research for in the Digital society
WYRED
WYRED Questionnaire for Children
To provide evidence of why / if children tell lies on the internet?

PLEASE CIRCLE YOUR ANSWER

1. Do you have access to the internet? Yes No

2. How often do you use the internet? Daily Weekly Monthly Other

3. Do you mainly use:

• Social media – eg Facebook, Snapchat, Instagram	Yes	No	Don't know
• Instant messaging- eg whatsapp, imessenger	Yes	No	Don't know
• Email	Yes	No	Don't know
• Facetime/Skype	Yes	No	Don't know
• You-tube	Yes	No	Don't know
• Gaming	Yes	No	Don't know
• Search engines such as google or other	Yes	No	Don't know
• Online educational tools eg mathematics/reading etc	Yes	No	Don't know
• Other – please specify	Yes	No	Don't know

4. How important is the internet in your life? 1 2 3 4 5 (1=Very Important/5=not important)

5. I sometimes feel left out when my friends talk about the internet. Agree Disagree

6. Some children do things on line that they wouldn't want their parents to know about. Agree Disagree

7. Do you have an online profile? Yes No

8. Are you totally honest about what you post online if no call you give 3 reasons why? Yes No

9. Do you think it is play to tell lies on the internet? if yes can you give 3 reasons why? Yes No

10. Many people admit to telling lies/not being totally honest on the internet? Agree Disagree

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Project title: Appeal to the European Parliament

Country: Austria

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/renewable-energies-alternatives/project/appeal-european-parliament>

Project title: Prison School - "Gefängnis Schule"

Country: Austria

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More information on WYRED platform: <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/hertha-firnberg-gruppe-austria/project/prison-school-gefängnis-schule>

Project title: Modern Technologies - and their Effects on Tourism Industry

Country: Austria

More information on WYRED platform: <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/new-technologies-tourism/project/modern-technologies-and-their-effects-tourism-industry>

Project title: Effects of Industry 4.0 on Tourism Industry - Development from E-Tourism to M-Tourism

Country: Austria

More information on WYRED platform: <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/new-technologies-tourism/project/effects-industry-40-tourism-industry-development-e>

Project title: Modern Slavery

Country: Austria

More information on WYRED platform: <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/hertha-firnberg-gruppe-austria/project/modern-slavery>

Project title: Trade Agreements within the European Union

Country: Austria

More information on WYRED platform:
<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/economy-and-trade-eu/project/trade-agreements-within-european-union>

Project title: Sedetka - this is my life

Country: Austria

More information on WYRED platform: <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/das-ist-die-eggenburg-gruppe-aus-österreich/project/sedetka-my-life>

Project title: Gaming - I love it!

Country: Austria

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More information on WYRED platform: <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/das-ist-die-eggenburg-gruppe-aus-österreich/project/gaming-i-love-it>

Project title: Mobbing

Country: Austria

More information on WYRED platform: <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/das-ist-die-eggenburg-gruppe-aus-österreich/project/mobbing>

Project title: Environmental pollution

Country: Austria

More information on WYRED platform: <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/das-ist-die-eggenburg-gruppe-aus-österreich/project/environmental-pollution>

Project title: Future professions

Country: Austria

More information on WYRED platform: <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/das-ist-die-eggenburg-gruppe-aus-österreich/project/future-professions>

Project title: Don't give up!

Country: Austria

More information on WYRED platform: <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/das-ist-die-eggenburg-gruppe-aus-österreich/project/dont-give>

Project title: How Italy is seen by other Countries

Country: Italy

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunitaitaliana/project/come-litalia-è-vista-dagli-altri-paesihow-italy-seen-other>

Project title: Globalisation. ONG's denounce and photographic evidence

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Country: Italy

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunita-italiana/project/fotografia-che-denuncia>

Project title: Prevention and contrast cyberbullying and bullying. How do institutions provide teachers with support for the phenomenon?

Country: Italy

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunita-italiana/project/prevention-and-contrast-cyberbullyingand-bulling-how-do>

Project title: Citizens' social and electoral participation

Country: Italy

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunitaitaliana/project/partecipazione-sociale-e-voto>

Project title: several research activities

Country: Belgium, Italy, Ukraine

Supporting material:

Session 1 (June 2017) - Brussels: <https://photos.app.goo.gl/Iuv5mckguakh2T8K2>

Session 2 (September 2017) - Lviv: <https://photos.app.goo.gl/A40OcRImQJITiu43>

Session 3 (December 2017) - Brussels :<https://photos.app.goo.gl/69V8VoEdt5Q2hJg02>

Session 4 (January 2018) - Tortona: <https://photos.app.goo.gl/bNfsqRD2UwJNhIvW2>

Session 5 (March 2018) - Tortona: <https://photos.app.goo.gl/f6oPsHZTgxun2nLO2>

Project title: Which level is better to cover employment prospects

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Country: Italy/ Belgium

More information on WYRED platform: [Survey Results](#)

Project title: The use of Digital as content in Education

Country: Italy/ Belgium

More information on WYRED platform:

[Survey Results](#)

Project title: Are young people aware of privacy and safety aspect when being online?

Country: Italy/ Belgium

More information on WYRED platform: [Survey Results - Report](#)

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Project title: "Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions: cultural development - can the virtual/digital tools help? how?"

Country: Italy/ Belgium

More information on WYRED platform: [Report](#)

Project title: "Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions at school - what's the perception of migrant students and how does the virtual world affect reality on this topic?"

Country: Italy/ Belgium

More information on WYRED platform: [Questionnaire IT](#)

Project title: La lucha de la existencia

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-lucha-la-existencia>

Project title: El efecto de la globalización en la educación

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/efecto-la-globalizaci%C3%B3n-la-educaci%C3%B3n>

Project title: Starbucks Rwanda Rift Valley

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/starbucks-rwanda-rift-valley>

Project title: Feminismo, inmigración ilegal, Sociedad y tradición

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/feminismo-inmigraci%C3%B3n-ilegal>

Project title: Ni una menos

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/ni-una-menos>

Project title: Una nueva Europa

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Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/una-nueva-europa>

Project title: The face of society

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/face-society>

Project title: El impacto de la globalización

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/impacto-la-globalizaci%C3%B3n>

Project title: Homofobia

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/homofobia>

Project title: Feminismo. ¿Cuánto sabe la gente?

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/feminismo-%C2%BFcu%C3%A1nto-sabe-la-gente>

Project title: La realidad de nuestra naturaleza

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-realidad-nuestra-naturaleza>

Project title: La desigualdad en sus distintos aspectos desde una visión global

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-desigualdad-sus-distintos>

Project title: La sociedad

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-sociedad>

Project title: Globalización, nación e identidad en el mundo actual

Country: Spain

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More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-identidad>

Project title: Alumnas inspiradas

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/alumnas-inspiradas>

Project title: La redes sociales en un mundo globalizado

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/las-redes-sociales-un-mundo>

Project title: No nos olvidemos de la realidad

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/no-nos-olvidemos-la-realidad>

Project title: El mundo actual

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/mundo-actual>

Project title: How to 3

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/how-3>

Project title: Globalización desde nuestra ciudad

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/globalizaci%C3%B3n-desde-nuestra-ciudad>

Project title: Influencia de la educación en nuestra vida

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/influencia-la-educaci%C3%B3n-nuestra-vida>

Project title: Feminismo

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

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<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/feminismo>

Project title: Un mar de plásticos

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/un-mar-pl%C3%A1sticos>

Project title: Cuento

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/cuento>

Project title: Radio Sol

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/radio-sol>

Project title: Paseo por la realidad

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/paseo-por-la-realidad>

Project title: La vida de Timmy

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-vida-timmy>

Project title: La globalización en el mundo

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-globalizaci%C3%B3n-mundo>

Project title: La globalización: origen y actualidad

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-globalizaci%C3%B3n-origen-y-actualidad>

Project title: Yihadismo

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

Advisory Board meeting 2
WP10_D10.3

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/yihadismo>

Project title: Cartas para no ser leídas

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/cartas-para-no-ser-le%C3%ADdas>

Project title: Un solo planeta

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/un-solo-planeta>

Project title: La Declaración unilateral de independencia de Cataluña. Historia de un nacionalismo

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-declaraci%C3%B3n-unilateral>

Project title: El terrorismo de ETA

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/terrorismo-eta>

Project title: Problemas de identidad personal

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/problemas-identidad-personal>

Project title: Guerra y evolución

Country: Spain

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/guerra-y-evoluci%C3%B3n>

Project title: Not drawn a scale

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/do%C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops>

Advisory Board meeting 2
WP10_D10.3

Project title: Filter machine

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/do%C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops>

Project title: Technological glove

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/do%C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops>

Project title: Smart filter

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/do%C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops>

Project title: Dentepate

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/do%C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops>

Project title: Water cleaning device (WCD)

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/do%C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops>

Advisory Board meeting 2
WP10_D10.3

Project title: Something cool

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%2C%2Fcommunity/project/do%2C%2Fideation-workshops>

Project title: Everything is better with air

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%2C%2Fcommunity/project/do%2C%2Fideation-workshops>

Project title: Rain arise

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%2C%2Fcommunity/project/do%2C%2Fideation-workshops>

Project title: Master regülatör box

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%2C%2Fcommunity/project/do%2C%2Fideation-workshops>

Project title: Smart Water (SMWR)

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%2C%2Fcommunity/project/do%2C%2Fideation-workshops>

Advisory Board meeting 2
WP10_D10.3

Project title: Miracle salt: the alternatives of new generation heat insulation with sodium sulfate

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%2C%2Fcommunity/project/doga-school-projects>

Project title: Don't be afraid know well!

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%2C%2Fcommunity/project/doga-school-projects>

Project title: The population change, social and spatial effects after refugee migrations in the last ten years of Istanbul

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%2C%2Fcommunity/project/doga-school-projects>

Project title: The environmentally friendly roofs: to obtain energy from rain water on the roofs shaped in the form of m

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%2C%2Fcommunity/project/doga-school-projects>

Project title: Sex-oriented idioms from past to today

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%2C%2Fcommunity/project/doga-school-projects>

Advisory Board meeting 2
WP10_D10.3

Project title: Zero waste with *Chlorella vulgaris*

Country: Turkey

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/doga-school-projects>

Project title: What's wrong with the education system

Country: Israel

More information on WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/shfayim>

8. References

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